

SHIHOBIDDIN SUHRAWARDI: THE INTERSECTION OF SUFISM AND ETHICS IN SPIRITUAL EDUCATION

Murtozoev Shahobiddin Bakhriddinovich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Senior lecturer of the Department of Social Sciences
in Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute
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Annotation: This article deeply analyzes the moral and educational significance of the Sufi-irfanian perspectives created by Shihobiddin Suhrawardi, demonstrating how his focus on inner knowledge and spiritual enlightenment serves as a foundation for moral development and the formation of ethical behavior. Additionally, the article emphasizes the importance of Suhrawardi's Sufi teachings in nurturing virtues such as humility, compassion, and honesty.

Key words: Sufism, sunnah, hadith, prophet, humanity, morality, spirituality, heredity, philosophy, society, justice, education.

Shihobiddin Suhrawardi's philosophical and sufistical perspectives are fundamentally based on the understanding of oneself, recognizing the Divine, and escaping the snares of the ego. He scientifically and theoretically substantiated the dangers of carnal and sensual desires for humanity. The Sufi believed that the process of human development begins with the refinement of inner ethics. He argued that it is impossible to achieve true perfection without cultivating the ego.

In this context, he particularly analyzed the vices of greed and hastiness. He illustrated the consequences of these vices and outlines the methods for eliminating them. In today's modern society, moral education has become significantly important. The legacy of Suhrawardi, particularly through the study of his ethical and educational views, is essential for developing ways to enhance educational processes.

Shihobuddin's sufistical-philosophical views were shaped by the style of thought and religious-philosophical perspectives of his time. His sufistical-philosophical beliefs stand out due to their subservience to ethical ideals. Indeed, human behavior and actions are interconnected with many factors. In this regard, he emphasized the ethics of Sufis and Sufi education, stating, "Sufis are the group that most closely follows the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and has the right to revive his Sunnah and embody beautiful ethics" [1]. During the Middle Ages, the status of Sufi sheikhs was very high. Their ethical experiences and educational methods were comprehensive and beneficial in the upbringing of disciples.

Suhravardiy addressed the issue of ethics by referring to the hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). He interpreted the following hadith narrated by Anas ibn Malik in a relevant manner: “The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) said to me: “O my son, when you wake up in the morning and when you lie down to sleep at night, strive to ensure that your heart does not harbor ill feelings towards anyone”. He then added, “This is my Sunnah. Whoever revives my Sunnah is like one who revives me, and whoever revives me will be with me in Paradise”. He also advised: “O my dear son! Cherish solitude! When you are alone, your heart will be in a state of humility before Allah. Only then can you become a servant worthy of Allah’s grace. In this world, behave like a stranger or a passerby! Leave this world as innocent and sinless as you arrived. For, you do not know how your name will be remembered on the Day of Judgment” [2].

Indeed, the paths taken by Sufis are the most noble paths, as they follow the path of the Prophet. For this reason, they initially adhered to his teachings in their states and emulated his actions during their experiences. Their efforts bore fruit, leading them to ultimately follow his ethics. Improving one’s character cannot be achieved without restraining the ego.

Suhravardiy stated that the ego is, on one hand, linked to inclination and nature, and on the other hand, it is related to character. The Sufi’s thoughts align with modern scientific understanding, distinguishing three crucial factors that influence an individual’s development: heredity, cultural environment, and living conditions [3]. As a result of the interaction among these factors, an individual develops a unique set of characteristics, corresponding needs, interests, clients, abilities, goals, intentions, spirituality, and so forth. One can conclude that Suhravardiy employed a dualistic approach in understanding humans. In his views, humanity is perceived as a being composed, on one hand, of a material organism and, on the other hand, of a non-material essence that governs this organism. Thus, Suhravardiy established that a person is both a biological and a social being in his work “Avorif ul-Ma’arif”

The meaning of the hadith of Rasulullah (peace be upon him): “Every newborn is born in a state of purity in Islam. Then, his parents raise him as a Jew, a Christian, or a Zoroastrian”, aligns with the aforementioned verses [1]. From the hadith of Rasulullah (peace be upon him), one can logically conclude that every human possesses the innate ability to recognize the existence of Allah, regardless of the religion they follow. The ability to understand and acknowledge God is inherently present in every individual, stemming from the

primordial covenant (mīthāq al-'alast) established long ago, which means it is preserved within every human being. However, due to improper upbringing, some individuals may either remain unaware of their innate understanding of God or completely suppress it. The philosopher Tabatabai has explained the concept of "mīthāq al-'alast" as follows: individuals, who come into the world at different times and places – from Adam (peace be upon him) until the Day of Resurrection – witness the Creator in a way that transcends time and space. They testify as if they are present at the same time and in the same place before Allah. While space and time are limited for humans, the Ever-Present and All-Aware Creator exists beyond those limitations. Thus, the experiences of two individuals, separated by millions of years or countless miles, can converge in a single moment and place when it comes to witnessing the Creator. [4]. Contemporary interpreters approach this issue from the perspective of genetics. According to their view, the belief and faith in the existence and unity of God is inherently present in every human being's nature. This awareness is transmitted from one generation to another primarily through genes.

In Shihobiddin Suhrawardiy's work, "Avorif ul-Ma'arif", there is a discussion regarding the character of Rasulullah (peace be upon him) based on a narration from Aisha (may Allah be pleased with her). It emphasizes that the soul (nafs) is a tool granted to humans for achieving perfection. If the soul were not bestowed upon them, individuals would remain in a singular state akin to angels, devoid of the experiences of elevation or descent. Allah, in His wisdom, has made the soul a unique feature of humanity, allowing for the blessings of divine revelation and the teachings of Rasulullah (peace be upon him) to resonate and be articulated [1]. It contained attributes and morals that were a mercy to the worlds. Through these, those great moral qualities, with a slight shadowy distinction from the states of Rasulullah, emerge in the souls of the ummah. The qualities that remained with Rasulullah became etiquettes, and when Allah revealed His firm verses, they drew strength from them, manifesting as a form of mercy specific to the Prophet. In due time, the ummah began to act upon these revealed verses collectively. According to Suhrawardiy, the most effective way to overcome the desires of the soul and to act against its inclinations is to live in accordance with the Sunnah and to keep the heart free from attachment to created beings.

In conclusion, Shihobiddin Suhrawardiy's sufistical and philosophical perspectives hold significant importance in the process of moral growth and education, finding their place in strengthening the moral values of contemporary society. Suhrawardiy's teachings aid each individual in discovering their inner

world and achieving true knowledge. This, in turn, contributes to ensuring goodness and justice in social life.

References:

1. سهروردی الدین شهاب. المعارف عوارف. № Buxoro davlat muzey qo'riqxonasi, hujjatlar fondi 21125/11. -B.209a.
2. Шаҳобиддин ас-Сухравардий. Васиятнома. тарж: Ҳамидуллоҳ Беруний. ШҚМ, № 2956/IX. – В. 165 b -167a.
3. Шермухаммедова Н. Фалсафа. –Т.: “Ношир”, 2012. –Б. 584.
4. Холмўминов Ж. Қиёсий тасаввуфшунослик (Монография). – Т.: 2021, 182 б.
5. BAHRIDDINOVICH, Murtazoyev Shahobiddin. The Spiritual Heritage of Abu Hafs Umar Suhrawardi and it's significance for the Contemporary World. Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History, 2021, 2.3: 53-60.
6. MURTOZAYEV, Shahobiddin. Abu Hafs Umar Suhrawardiy inson nafsini anglashga doir falsafiy qarashlarining tahlili. Farg'ona davlat universiteti, 2023, 1: 192-192.
7. BAXRIDDINOVICH, Murtozayev Shahobiddin. Shihabuddin al-Suhrawardi's views on sufism and his scientific heritage in central asia. 2023.
8. BAXRIDDINOVICH, Murtozayev Shahobiddin. SHIHABIDDIN SUHRAWARDY'S VIEWS ON ETHICS. Innovative Developments And Research In Education, 2023, 2.16: 11-16.
9. BAXRIDDINOVICH, Murtozayev Shahobiddin. SHIHABIDDIN SUHRAWARDY'S VIEWS ON ETHICS. Innovative Developments And Research In Education, 2023, 2.16: 11-16.
10. МУРТОЗАЕВ, Шаҳобиддин. SHIHOBUDDIN UMAR SUXRAVARDIYNING “AVORIF UL-MAORIF” ASARI VA UNDA ILGARI SURILGAN G'OYALAR. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 2023, 3.S/8.